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3 **Resolving the thickness of peat deposits with contact-less electromagnetic**
4 **methods: a case study in the Venice coastland**

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6 Boaga J. ⁽¹⁾, Viezzoli A. ⁽²⁾, Cassiani G. ⁽¹⁾, Deidda G.P. ⁽³⁾, Tosi L. ⁽⁴⁾, Silvestri S. ^{(5)*}

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8 ⁽¹⁾ Dept. of Geosciences, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

9 ⁽²⁾ Aarhus Geophysics ApS, Aarhus, Denmark

10 ⁽³⁾ Dept. of Civil and Environmental Engineering and Architecture, University of
11 Cagliari, Cagliari, Italy

12 ⁽⁴⁾ Institute of Geosciences and Earth Resources, National Research Council, Via G.
13 Gradenigo, 6 - 35131 Padova, Italy, luigi.tosi@igg.cnr.it

14 ⁽⁵⁾ Dept. of Biological, Geological and Environmental Sciences, University of Bologna,
15 Ravenna, Italy

16 * corresponding author

17
18 **Abstract**

19 Peat soils are typical deposits characterizing wetlands and reclaimed farmlands. They
20 are important carbon reservoirs and when degraded (e.g., erosive processes, fires,
21 draining and plowing) massive carbon dioxide volumes are released. This leads to
22 increase greenhouse effect and induce serious land subsidence. Thus, mapping the
23 volume of peat deposits is crucial in order to estimate the carbon mass and the potential
24 release of carbon dioxide and consequent loss in soil elevation. Despite the importance
25 of such estimations, forecasting and quantifying the peat thickness is still a challenge.

26 Direct sediment coring provides local information that are difficult to extend to large
27 territories. ~~Indirect geophysical methods are unable to resolve lithological contrasts in~~
28 ~~the presence of saltwater contamination in coastal areas. Indirect geophysical methods~~
29 ~~are often vanished by the presence of saltwater contamination in coastal areas.~~ In this
30 work, we show the results obtained using two contact-less electromagnetic methods for
31 the characterization of peat deposits in a peatland site of the Venice coastland, Italy.
32 Specifically, a multi-frequency portable instrument (FDEM) and an airborne time-
33 domain electromagnetic one (AEM) were used to collect data over a former wetland
34 then reclaimed for agricultural purposes. Additional electrical resistivity tomography
35 (ERT) data, ~~which are~~ known for their very high and relatively low vertical resolution
36 respectively, are used together with sediment core data to assess the effectiveness and
37 accuracy of the contact-less methods. Results show that both FDEM and AEM are very
38 effective in detecting the presence of the peat layer, despite its low thickness (< 2 m)
39 and the high electro-conductive subsoil because of saltwater contamination. However,
40 the AEM method overestimated the peat thickness while the FDEM could accurately
41 resolve the peat thickness even where the layer was thinner than 1 m. When compared
42 to the electrical features extracted from the ERT, discrepancies are on average lower
43 than 30-%; when compared to the borehole data, discrepancies are on average slightly
44 higher than 6-%.

Commented [DSSP1]: Line 25: Suggest rephrasing the sentence beginning in this line. The verb "vanish" is poor English usage in this context. Try either of these sentences: "Indirect geophysical methods do not work well in the presence of saltwater contamination in coastal areas." OR "Indirect geophysical methods are unable to resolve lithological contrasts in the presence of saltwater contamination in coastal areas."

45

46 1. Introduction

47 Peatlands are important carbon pools and, if degraded, they release large amounts of
48 carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gasses (Page et al., 2002; Turetsky et al., 2015).
49 The organic carbon stored belowground is preserved by wet or moist soil conditions.

50 Once the soil is drained, as for example during prolonged droughts or for man-induced
51 processes such as land reclamation, aerobic microorganisms decompose quickly the
52 organic matter, releasing carbon dioxide and other gasses (e.g., Hooijer et al., 2012;
53 Fenner and Freeman, 2011). The decomposition of organic matter also induces one of
54 the most severe mechanisms of land subsidence, i.e. the geochemical subsidence
55 (Zanello et al., 2011), which may cause meters of loss in ground elevation in a few
56 decades.

57 At the global scale, the large majority of terrestrial carbon is stored in soils. It is
58 estimated that vegetation stores about 500 Pg of carbon (considering both aboveground
59 and belowground phytomass) while soils store between 1500 Pg (Scherlemann et al.,
60 2014) and 2500 Pg (Batjes, 2014; Jansson et al., 2010) of carbon, and ~ 30% of it is
61 stored in peatlands (Scherlemann et al., 2014; Bourgeau-Chavez et al., 2018). Peat
62 degradation has been proven to contribute an enormous amount of greenhouse gasses
63 to the atmosphere every year. The estimate of the global emission of CO_{2eq} due to
64 peatland drainage is very uncertain, and varies between 0.9 and 1.3 Gt CO_{2eq}/yr
65 (Joosten, 2010; FAOSTAT, 2013). This picture is even more alarming if we consider
66 that the numerous fires that occur in forested wetland systems, especially in tropical
67 areas, increase the amount of greenhouse gasses released every year (Turetsky et al.,
68 2015; Ballhorn et al., 2009). In addition to the problems related to CO_{2eq} emissions, the
69 continuous conversion of tropical peatlands to agriculture and the hydraulic drainage
70 of low-lying areas have resulted in widespread land subsidence creating great concern
71 especially in coastal areas (e.g., Van Asselen et al., 2018).

72 Considering that the potential of releasing carbon dioxide and of peatland subsidence
73 depends on the mass availability of the organic matter in the soil, the quantification of
74 the peat extent over vast territories is a very relevant challenge. **Therefore, it is**

75 becoming urgent to develop methodologies that allow an accurate and fast mapping of
76 soil organic carbon, with particular interest for wetlands and peatlands.

77 The most common and widely used method for peat deposit quantification and
78 characterization relies on shallow borehole information and ground-based surveys
79 using geophysical methods. In order to be effective at the regional scale and given the
80 extent and thickness variability of peat, a method based on field measurements needs a
81 large database of high-density distributed field observations, which are essential in
82 order to correctly define the covariance model necessary to interpolate/extrapolate the
83 point measurements (Keaney et al., 2013) and minimize spatial aliasing. In the
84 literature, there are examples of studies reporting the collection of a large number of
85 peat thickness measurements performed in the field using push probes (Parsekian et al.,
86 2012; Householder et al., 2012; Holden and Connolly, 2011). However, even though
87 the use of push probes is a relatively fast method and may provide large databases, it
88 has been shown that the accuracy reached using exclusively soil probes is limited,
89 leading to an average error of depth estimation as high as 35% (Parry et al., 2014). Soil
90 coring guarantees much higher accuracies in measuring the peat thickness locally,
91 however it is extremely time consuming especially in wetland environments and does
92 not allow the collection of large enough databases. In order to overcome these issues,
93 various traditional ground-based geophysical techniques have been successfully
94 applied for peat characterization. For example, ground penetrating radar (GPR) (e.g.,
95 Comas et al. 2017; Comas et al., 2015; Parsekian et al., 2012; Slater and Reeve, 2002),
96 electrical tomography (ERT) (e.g., Walter et al. 2019; Comas et al., 2015; Elijah et al.,
97 2012; Boon et al., 2008;) and induced polarization (IP) methods (e.g., Comas and Slater,
98 2004; Slater and Reeve, 2002) together with complementary borehole data.

Commented [DSSP2]: Line 95: change complement to complementary

99 Nevertheless, the use of soil cores and traditional ground-based geophysical techniques
100 are generally limited, being moist and wet soil conditions difficult accessible and the
101 relatively local scale of the investigations obtainable. ~~Moreover, the presence of dense~~
102 ~~vegetation cover peatlands are usually covered with very dense vegetation that~~
103 represents an additional challenge for traditional ground-based geophysics.

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104 Recently, Silvestri et al. (2019a, 2019b) used airborne electro-magnetic (AEM) to
105 identify peat layers over large territories in a Norwegian study site characterized by the
106 presence of several bogs and in a large Indonesian peatland respectively. In both these
107 frameworks, the AEM method proved to be highly effective to distinguish the electrical
108 properties of the peat layer from that of the substrate, ~~allowing delineation of their~~

Commented [DSSP4]: Lines 106-107. Change the phrase "allowing to drawn their boundary" to "allowing delineation of their boundaries."

109 ~~boundaries~~ ~~allowing to drawn their boundary~~. Higher vertical resolution is obtained with
110 the presence of conductive substrate while the uncertainty increases for resistive
111 substrates. However, through a sensitivity analysis, Silvestri et al. (2019a, 2019b) show
112 that the accuracy reached using exclusively the AEM method is generally not sufficient
113 to resolve thin peat layers, roughly 1-1.5 m thick. Therefore, an alternative approach is
114 needed to investigate thin peat layers over large areas.

115 In this paper, we present the results obtained by testing for the first time a contact-less
116 frequency domain electromagnetic method (FDEM) for resolving the peat thickness.
117 The main advantage of this method is that it is suitable for meso-scale peatland
118 characterization of difficult-to-access areas, but also tries to overcome the limited
119 vertical resolution that affects the AEM technology. A comparison of the vertical
120 accuracies obtained with both AEM and FDEM methods is also performed and
121 discussed.

122 The pilot area selected for this study is a low-lying peatland used for farmland, located
123 between the Po river delta and the Venice Lagoon, Italy. Most of the farmland is derived

124 from the hydraulic reclamations of ancient wetlands and lagoons, which started at the
125 beginning of the last century, and today lies below mean sea level.

126 Information on the peat thickness is very limited as it is available only from sediment
127 cores, which provide local details. In general, the peat layer thickness is lower than 2
128 m because the original uppermost layers were oxidized during the last century due to
129 the hydraulic drainage and agricultural activities, which induced geochemical
130 subsidence (Tosi et al., 2009). Tosi et al. (2000) computed rates of up to 3-4 cm/yr of
131 loss in elevation during the last century. Such large historical rates come from a number
132 of concomitant causes of land subsidence that included (i) the groundwater pumping
133 occurred in the 1950-1960 period (contributing about 1-1.5 m to the total subsidence),
134 (ii) exploitation of gas-bearing waters (from late 1940s to late 1960s), (iii) the common
135 practice of burning grass and vegetation that grew along the banks of the hydraulic
136 drainage network causing the peat to burn. In addition, the maintenance of a very low
137 water table (by pumping stations) during rainy periods in order to avoid sudden floods
138 increased for decades the oxidation of organic soils and therefore facilitated the
139 geochemical subsidence. Today, groundwater exploitation and the agriculture practice
140 of burning vegetation are no longer used, and the beginning of 2000's the hydraulic
141 reclamation drainage management allows to keep the water table higher than in the past,
142 significantly reducing land subsidence rates. Even though the rates are considerably
143 smaller than in the past, it has been shown that the land is still subsiding at a rate of 3-
144 15 mm/yr, calculated for the recent years (Zanello et al., 2011) releasing in the
145 atmosphere $9.2 \pm 5.5 \text{ kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-2}$ (Camporese et al., 2008).

146 The selected case study is particularly challenging from the geophysical point of view
147 because thin peat deposits are hard to distinguish from the underlying conductive
148 substrate that consists of clay and silty-clay layers, often salinized by saltwater

149 intrusion. In fact, the organic matter present in peat soils has similar electrical properties
150 to conductive substrates (Silvestri et al. 2019b), producing a modest resistivity contrast
151 that makes it problematic to detect the discontinuity at the bottom of the peat. Despite
152 the challenges, our findings show that contact-less geophysical methods as FDEM and
153 AEM can successfully detect the presence of peat deposits. While AEM tends to
154 overestimate the peat thickness of thin peat deposits, FDEM can accurately resolve also
155 very thin peat layers.

156

157 2. Study site

158 The study site is the Zennare basin, which is part of a larger low-lying area located
159 between the southern margin of the Venice Lagoon and the northern Po river delta
160 (Italy) (Fig. 1). The area is characterized by Holocene deposits with a variety of
161 geomorphic features, as for example ancient fluvial ridges, paleo-river beds and paleo-
162 coastlines (Rizzetto et al. 2003). The basin is currently below the mean sea level and it
163 mostly consists of high value agricultural land established after the hydraulic
164 reclamation of pre-existing lagoons and wetland areas that started in the Veneto Region
165 in 1892. Today, the basin is surrounded by levees; ditches regulate the surface waters
166 and pumping stations stabilize the water table at about 0.5 m below the land surface,
167 discharging the drainage water into the Venice Lagoon or the Adriatic Sea.

168 Over the past century, oxidation of the organic soil fraction in response to drainage for
169 farming provoked the degradation of the shallow peat deposits leading to serious land
170 subsidence rates, often one order of magnitude higher than the natural ones caused by
171 sediment compaction and tectonic movements (e.g., Tosi et al., 2009; Tosi et al., 2010;
172 Tosi et al., 2016). Evidence of peat-oxidation land settlements, e.g., the protrusion of

173 old hydraulic structures founded on the stiff clays and sands underlying the outcropping
174 peat, and ground- and satellites-based monitoring data allowed to quantify up to 2-3
175 cm/yr of loss in surface elevation (Tosi et al., 2000; Gambolati et al., 2005; Tosi et al.,
176 2016). Consequently, the basin today lays between 2 and 4 m below the mean sea level
177 (Rizzetto et al., 2003; Gasparetto-Stori et al., 2012). Ridges corresponding to sand filled
178 paleochannel systems not affected by geochemical subsidence due to oxidation of the
179 organic matter show higher elevations than the nearby peat soils.

180 The outcropping peat deposits extend for most of the basin (e.g., Nicoletti et al., 2003).
181 The large majority of the shallow peats originally present in the area have been
182 degraded due to geochemical subsidence as consequence of the oxidation of the organic
183 soil. Currently the thickness of the peat layer is almost half of the original one and varies
184 between less than 1 m to a maximum of 2 m across the basin (Rizzetto et al., 2003).

185 The shallow sequence is constituted by a c.a. 50 cm of ploughed and oxidized soil at
186 the top and a peat with well-preserved fibers in growing position at the bottom. At the
187 base, there is a transition layer of clayey peat gradually passing to clay with spread
188 vegetable remains (Gatti et al., 2001). Peats derive from the accumulation of reeds
189 (*Phragmites australis*) living in wetlands before the reclamation (Gatti et al., 2001).

190 Soil salt contamination partly affects the Zennare Basin (e.g., Rizzetto et al., 2003). The
191 saltwater intrusion is favored by the land elevation that is well below the mean sea level
192 but also by the presence of sandy paleo-channels crossing the farmland with main
193 direction from inland to the lagoon boundary.

194
 195 **Fig. 1 – The Zennare basin is outlined in yellow.** The map inset on the top-right shows
 196 the location of the basin with respect to the Venice lagoon (Italy). The red lines
 197 correspond to the AEM flight lines. The white rectangle shows the location of the
 198 ground-based field surveys and is magnified within the inset to the left of the figure,
 199 where the orange dots indicate the shallow boreholes, the purple line corresponds to the
 200 FDEM transect and the short light-blue line shows the location of the ERT transect.

201

202 3. Methods

203 The dataset collected and analyzed in this study includes (see Fig. 1 for locations): (i)
 204 frequency domain ground-based electro-magnetic (FDEM) data, (ii) ERT data along
 205 **the initial portion of the FDEM transect, (iii) an aerial AEM survey along 2 flight-lines,**
 206 **and (iv) borehole data collected along the FDEM transect, in order to get lithological**
 207 **information and peat layer thickness.**

208 With reference to other studies carried out in the Venice coastland (e.g., Carbognin et
209 al., 2003; de Franco et al., 2009; Viezzoli et al., 2009; Teatini et al., 2011; Da Lio et al.,
210 2015), electrical resistivity $<5 \Omega \cdot m$ and $>10 \Omega \cdot m$ are respectively the upper and lower
211 values for saltwater and freshwater, in terms of the electro-lithological units.

212 3.1 Frequency Domain Electro-Magnetic (FDEM) survey

213 The FDEM survey was performed in Fall 2018 using a GEM-2 probe manufactured by
214 Geophex (www.geophex.com). The FDEM system is a multi-frequency probe, capable
215 of investigating electrical properties of several depths at the same time (e.g., Boaga,
216 2017, 2018; Deidda et al., 2014). The probe has one transmitter and one receiver coils,
217 with a fixed separation of 1.66 m, and a multifrequency operation in the bandwidth 30
218 Hz - 93 kHz. GEM-2 can be used as a conductivity meter for depth sounding when it
219 operates in a range of moderate induction number (McNeill, 1980), for which the
220 responses are strong and frequency dependent (Huang and Won, 2003). To meet this
221 requirement, as the area is underlined by fairly conductive sediments, we used six
222 frequencies ($f_1 = 1,250$ Hz, $f_2 = 4,250$ Hz, $f_3 = 10,025$ Hz, $f_4 = 21,750$ Hz, $f_5 = 30,025$
223 Hz, and $f_6 = 47,025$ Hz) in order to span the range of induction numbers between 0.1166
224 and 0.7152, and assuming the worst condition of a nonmagnetic half-space with a
225 conductivity equal to 1 S/m.

226 The GEM-2 probe was carried by the operator along a 700 m NW-SE transect (see Fig.
227 1 for location), at a constant height of about 1 m from the surface. The FDEM probe
228 was connected to a Trimble GPS receiver to record the spatial coordinates for each
229 measurement (with a total of about 12,000 points). Raw data were then processed
230 focusing on the area where ERT data and control boreholes (03 and 04) are available
231 (see section 3.3).

232 Prior to the inversion, data collected along the first 200 m of the transect were spatially
 233 resampled at 1 m interval to set up a data set consisting of a series of 201 geometric
 234 depth soundings with six complex (quadrature and in-phase components) GEM-2
 235 responses. The complex response recorded at each sounding point was individually
 236 inverted to infer the electrical conductivity depth profile using the FDEMtools (Deidda
 237 et al., 2019), a free MATLAB software package implementing the numerical algorithms
 238 mainly discussed by Deidda et al. (2014, 2017).
 239 A layered starting model, with the layer conductivities based on ERT results, was used
 240 for all one-dimensional inversions. In addition, to best fit the in-phase data at lower
 241 frequencies, the relative magnetic permeability was set at 0.995 (i.e., a magnetic
 242 susceptibility of -0.005 , a value representative of diamagnetic materials) in the top 1
 243 m portion of the model. As shown in Deidda et al. (2020), in this case too the inversion
 244 of the complex signals has provided better results than the inversion of the quadrature
 245 (imaginary part) component of the secondary to primary magnetic field ratio alone,
 246 reaching root mean squared errors lower than 10%. Fig. 2 shows two examples of data
 247 fitting, which relate to electromagnetic soundings co-located with boreholes 03 (Fig.
 248 2a) and 04 (Fig. 2b).

250 Fig. 2 – Quadrature (red) and in-phase (blue) components of the secondary magnetic
251 field response (ppm of the primary) as a function of frequency for electromagnetic
252 soundings at 24 m (a) and 142 m (b) from the beginning of the FDEM transect. Stars
253 and squares represent measured and predicted data, respectively.

254

255 3.2 Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) data

256 Along the first portion of the selected transect we also acquired an ERT transect with
257 the purpose of calibrating and comparing the resulting electrical resistivity values with
258 those obtained using the FDEM method. We adopted a 48 electrodes setup with 0.5 m
259 electrode spacing, for a total ERT length of 23.5 m. This ensures a depth of
260 investigation of about 5 m (1/4-1/5 of the ERT line length).

261 We used a dipole-dipole skip 0 configuration – i.e. with dipole lengths equal to the
262 minimum electrode spacing - collecting both direct and reciprocal measurements, in
263 order to control the quality of the raw data (e.g., Cassiani et al., 2006). Data were
264 collected with a Iris Instrument Syscal Pro resistivity meter, and were then inverted
265 using the R2 code (e.g., Binley, 2015). The collected dataset is of high quality, since
266 the 96% of the data pass the reciprocals check using a 5% error threshold.

267 3.3 Airborne Time Electro-Magnetic (AEM) data

268 Airborne Time Electro-Magnetic (AEM) data were collected in Fall 2013 in the context
269 of the National Flagship Project RITMARE (Tosi et al., 2018). The project aimed at
270 providing a step forward in the delineation of the continental and marine surface water–
271 groundwater interactions and the mechanisms controlling the saltwater intrusion,
272 overcoming the intrinsic constraints typical of ground-based surveys. Within the

273 RITMARE framework, the SkyTEM helicopter-deployed time domain electro-
274 magnetic system was chosen as its dual moment provides a bandwidth (i.e. a penetration
275 range) suitable for applications where both near-surface and deep information is
276 important to refine the hydrogeologic model (e.g., Teatini et al., 2011; Sørensen &
277 Auken, 2004). During the flight, current flows through a transmitter loop carried below
278 the helicopter at an altitude of about 30 m, setting up a magnetic field. The eddy currents
279 induced below the ground surface generate a secondary magnetic field, and a receiver
280 coils on the frame detects its temporal variation. SkyTEM data have been recently
281 proven very effective in characterizing peatlands in boreal and tropical areas (Silvestri
282 et al. 2019a, 2019b).

283 The AEM data have been re-processed in order to attempt to maximize the accuracy for
284 the detection of the near-surface soil layers. The data have then been inverted using two
285 homogeneous starting models, with initial conductivity of 30 $\Omega\cdot\text{m}$ and 5 $\Omega\cdot\text{m}$. For
286 both cases, the inversion was performed using 40 and 5 layers.

287 **3.4 Shallow borehole data**

288 The field surveys were performed in Fall 2018 and Spring 2019. The thickness of the
289 peat layer was measured at six locations localized using GPS (Tab. 1). The samples
290 were retrieved using an auger peat corer with diameter of 2.5 cm and 50 cm length.
291 Mechanical extensions were used in order to reach the bottom of the peat layer and
292 characterize the transition surface towards the sand below. A small sample of substrate
293 was collected at each location in order to determine its characteristics.

294 Geological and hydrogeological data collected within previous research projects and
295 available through the websites of Città Metropolitana Venezia

296 (<http://webgis.cittametropolitana.ve.it/geologia>) have also been used to support the
 297 validation and interpretation of the geophysical outcomes.

298

299 **4. Results**

300 Tab. 1 summarizes the outcomes for all the boreholes and includes a sample lithology
 301 corresponding to borehole 01 (see Fig. 1 for location). All shallow boreholes show a
 302 similar lithology, which includes a layer of peat in the uppermost portion, with a
 303 transition zone characterized by mud mixed with peat and silty-clay underneath.

304 The thickness of the peat deposits is very thin and has a pronounced spatial variability
 305 ranging from 83 cm (borehole 06) to 210 cm (borehole 2) (Tab. 1), with an average
 306 value of 134 cm and standard deviation of 54 cm.

307 The analysis of other cores taken in the Zennare Basin (Gatti et al., 2001; Carbognin
 308 and Tosi, 2003; Città Metropolitana di Venezia) confirms the fairly homogenous
 309 lithology with variable thickness of the peat layer. Sands and silts are found only in
 310 correspondence of paleo-channels.

311

312

313 Tab. 1 – Data corresponding to the boreholes and sample lithology found for borehole

314 **01.**

315

316 As explained in the Methods section, we inverted the multi-frequency FDEM data
317 collected along a 200 m long transect overlapping the ERT line and the control borehole
318 03 and 04.

319 The resulting one-dimensional models, with 60 layers to a depth of 6 m below the
320 ground surface, are stitched together and plotted as a pseudo two-dimensional section
321 in Fig. 3. The electrical resistivities vary gradually in the lateral direction, although they
322 have been obtained by inverting data, sounding by sounding, without any lateral
323 constraint. This is in agreement with the ERT evidence shown below in Fig.4.

324 Moreover, in agreement with the borehole information, the FDEM data substantially
325 divide the Zennare subsoil in 2 layers: an upper resistive layer with about 1 m thickness
326 lying on an electrically conductive subsurface. The first, with resistivities up to $50 \Omega \cdot m$,
327 represents the peat deposits, while the latter, with resistivities less than $12 \Omega \cdot m$, is
328 representative of the silty/clayey – clayey saturated layers (similar values can be found
329 e.g. in the fine sediments of the Venice lagoon - e.g. Boaga et al., 2014). In this very
330 conductive environment, the peat deposits appear to be more resistive ($>12 \Omega \cdot m$) in
331 agreement with what already observed at other sites (Silvestri et al., 2019a, 2019b;
332 Kowalczyk et al., 2017; Boon et al., 2008). These results confirm a substantial
333 agreement with the information coming from the shallow boreholes, confirming that
334 the average thickness of the peat layer in the study site is ~ 1.3 m. Specifically,
335 considering the $12 \Omega \cdot m$ resistivity threshold as the bottom of the peat layer and
336 averaging all the thickness values corresponding to such threshold along the transect,
337 we obtain a mean peat thickness of 128 cm, with a difference of 6 cm with the average
338 value calculated from boreholes in that zone.

339

340 Fig. 3 - Inverted electrical resistivity profile obtained from the FDEM multi-frequency

341 data. The dashed line indicates the 12 $\Omega \cdot m$ contour line as in Fig. 4. The location of the

342 ERT line (Fig. 4) is marked to the left. Tab.1 borehole lithology is also presented.

343

344

345

346

347

348 Fig. 4 - ERT inverted resistivity section (Fig.1 for location). The uppermost peat layer
349 is more resistive than the underlying silty clay layer having a lower electrical resistivity
350 ($< 12 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$). The dashed line indicates the $12 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$ contour line as in Fig. 3.

351

352 The resistivity values retrieved using the ERT profile are shown in Fig. 4 for
353 comparison with the FDEM inversion in Fig. 3. The ERT and FDEM results agree to a
354 very large extent: the shallow electrically resistive layer (values $> 12 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$) lies on a
355 conductive layer below. The contact between the two layers is at about 1 m depth, and
356 this coincides with the transition between the peat and the underlying silty/clay layer
357 (dashed line in Figs. 3-4), as detected by the direct borehole investigations. The ERT
358 data confirm the continuity of the peat layer across the study site with no substantial
359 lateral variations.

360 The results obtained from the inversion of the longest (northern) AEM flight line (see
361 location in Fig. 1) are shown in Fig. 5. In this case 40 layers and initial conductivity of
362 $30 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$ were used. Similar profiles were extracted for the second AEM flight line (the
363 southern one) given the same initial conditions. Other inversions were performed in
364 order to test the consistency of the method, and the results are shown in fig. A1 of the
365 Appendix (i.e. four inversion setups are shown: a) 40 layers and starting with initial
366 conductivity of $30 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$; b) 40 layers and starting with initial conductivity of $5 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$; c)
367 5 layers and starting with initial conductivity of $30 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$; d) 5 layers and starting with
368 initial conductivity of $5 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$). Note that the initial resistivity value in the inversion has
369 small to no influence on the final resistivity model, indicating that the model quickly
370 loses memory of the initial conditions, and that the inversion is robust. The similarity
371 of the results obtained with the inversions performed using 40 layers and 5 layers tells
372 us that the inversion consistently detects a more resistive surface layer over a

373 conductive substrate. This indicates that, despite the different resolution capabilities
374 due to the remote sensing setup, the results obtained using the AEM method confirm
375 the presence of an upper resistive layer corresponding to the peat deposit (Fig. 5).

376
377 Fig. 5 – Extracted of the AEM results along line A falling within the white rectangle in
378 Fig. 1. Here, like for ERT and FDEM results, the uppermost resistive layer ($>12 \Omega \cdot m$ -
379 peat) overlies the more conductive substrate ($< 12 \Omega \cdot m$ – silty clay). The dashed line
380 indicates the $12 \Omega \cdot m$ contour line.

381
382 Even though the AEM flight-line does not overlap with the ERT and FDEM transects
383 and with the borehole investigations, we can conclude that AEM is in substantial
384 agreement with the results obtained with the other methods. In fact, the AEM method
385 can detect the presence of the peat layer, even though it is very thin, and the resistivity
386 values detected by AEM are in good agreement with those obtained with ground based
387 FDEM and ERT. As for the peat thickness, if we consider the $12 \Omega \cdot m$ resistivity
388 threshold as we did for the FDEM inverted data, we obtain for the AEM data an average
389 peat thickness of 260 cm, which is considerably higher than the average value
390 calculated for FDEM (128 cm) and from boreholes (134 cm). We can conclude that

391 AEM tends to overestimate the peat thickness and this is probably due to a low vertical
392 resolution in a very-near-surface framework.

393

394 5. Discussion

395 Coastal wetlands are among the ecosystems that have mostly changed over the last
396 century, especially those converted to agricultural lands by hydraulic reclamations. The
397 soil rich in organic matter and peat layers makes farmlands highly productive, as in the
398 case of the selected study site. However, the drainage systems necessary for keeping
399 the water table level below the ground surface together with the plowing activities, are
400 responsible of massive carbon dioxide release. This process likely increases greenhouse
401 gasses and relative sea level rise because of the geochemical land subsidence triggered
402 by the oxidation of organic matter.

403 Understanding how peatlands contribute to these processes requires detailed knowledge
404 on the peat layer thickness. In general, the areal extent of the peatlands can be retrieved
405 by satellite images (e.g., Nicoletti et al., 2003; Ballhorn et al., 2011; Draper et al., 2014;
406 Jaenicke et al., 2008) while the assessment of their thickness over large areas is a
407 challenge, especially where the peat layer is thinner than 1-2 m and saltwater
408 contamination affect the shallow subsoil. In these environmental conditions, in fact,
409 organic soil, peat and saturated clay are expected to have similar electrical properties.
410 Peat is expected to have slightly higher resistivity with respect to the underlying clayey
411 materials, with resistivity values for the peat in the order of 20-50 $\Omega \cdot m$ (compare e.g.
412 with Kowalczyk et al., 2017). Ground-contact geophysical methods, such as ERT, have
413 been extensively used in previous studies to resolve peat thickness and electrical
414 characteristics (Boon et al., 2008; Comas et al., 2015; Elijah et al., 2012). Our
19

415 experience confirms that ERT, applied to our study site, provides excellent results and
416 high-resolution imaging, and is able to discern peat resistivity properties from the
417 silty/clayey layers. However, when the peat layer is thin, ERT data must be collected
418 with very small electrodes spacing in order to characterize the peat with high vertical
419 resolution. In our case study, for example, we used a distance between electrodes of 0.5
420 m, and a better resolution would require an even smaller spacing. This implies that if
421 the targets are thin peat layers, and the area to be covered is large, field-work can
422 quickly become overwhelming in terms of time and manpower. Thus, a demand for
423 faster and still accurate subsoil investigation methods is pressing.

424 Contact-less methods, if properly applied, have the advantage of providing fast results
425 for the characterization of large territories. Moreover, contact-less instruments can be
426 easily carried for long distances, across difficult-to-access territories, permanently
427 flooded or covered with dense vegetation. Our results show that such methods can be
428 very effective in detecting the presence of peat layers, both from ground based and
429 helicopter deployed sensors (i.e. FDEM and AEM method respectively). We show that,
430 if compared to the results obtained with ERT at the Zennare site, the contact-less ground
431 based FDEM technique and the remote airborne EM are both able to detect the presence
432 of the peat layer patterns and estimate the same range of resistivity values for peat and
433 subsoil. Our results show that, for conductive substrates, the peat presence can be
434 detected using AEM even when the peat layer is very thin; however, we also show that
435 AEM tends to overestimate the peat thickness. This result confirms the tendency of
436 AEM to overestimating thin peat layers that was found by Silvestri et al. (2019b) in
437 case of peats over conductive substrates in an Indonesian study site. On the contrary,
438 FDEM shows a superior accuracy in resolving the peat thickness, even for very thin
439 peat deposits. If we consider $12 \Omega \cdot m$ as the threshold value that separates the peat layer

440 from the substrate, we have on average a difference of less than 10 cm between the
441 average peat thickness resolved by the FDEM instrument along the transect and the
442 average thickness measured through probing. Such difference increases to 130 cm for
443 the AEM data. Even if we must notice that the AEM flight lines do not overlap with the
444 FDEM/ERT transect, we speculate that the difference is mainly due to the low vertical
445 resolution of the AEM and not to an actual variability of the peat layer thickness, which
446 is highly unfeasible at this study site. Note that, had we performed a contemporary
447 FDEM and AEM campaign over common transects, a joint inversion of ground-based
448 and airborne EM data would be possible and may potentially improve the final accuracy
449 of the retrievals.

450 These considerations open up to new perspectives for the characterization of extended
451 peatlands with contact-less and, in general, remote geophysical methods.

452

453 6. Conclusions

454 Contact-less electromagnetic methods represent a valid alternative to classic ground-
455 based geophysical methods for peat thickness detection. ~~Selected a~~ peatland located
456 South of the Venice lagoon (Italy) ~~was selected as our study site,-;~~ we compared the
457 results obtained by the inversion of -multi-frequency ground-based FDEM and airborne
458 time domain EM data to data coming from direct probing and detailed high resolution
459 ERT.]

460 The inverted results obtained from FDEM and AEM are in agreement with those
461 obtained with the ERT detecting a resistive peat layer lying over a conductive clay
462 substrate: the upper layer, about 1 m thick, shows a slightly larger electrical resistivity
463 ($> 25 \Omega \cdot m$) than the underlying conductive layer with lower resistivity ($< 12 \Omega \cdot m$).

21

Commented [DSSP5]: Lines 459-460: Delete the word "Selected" in line 459 and add "as our study site" in line 460.

464 These features are in agreement with the information available on the site from shallow
465 borehole drilling, confirming a peat thickness that varies between 80 cm and 130 cm
466 across the selected transect, over a silty/clayey substrate.

467 Our results show that both contact-less electro-magnetic methods used in this study
468 (FDEM and AEM) are effective in detecting the presence and electrical characteristics
469 of peat layers over conductive substrates, potentially allowing for very fast and
470 extended exploration surveys over large peatland sites, with a large saving of time and
471 fieldwork if compared to traditional ground-based methods. The main difference
472 between the two contact-less methods tested in our work lies on the accuracy in
473 resolving the peat thickness. If the peat deposit thickness is large, the airborne AEM
474 method can be adopted, allowing high accuracies over large territories (Silvestri et al.,
475 2019a, 2019b). In case of thin peat deposits, FDEM provides higher vertical resolutions
476 than AEM, substantially increasing the peat thickness mapping accuracy. We speculate
477 that ground-based and airborne data can be used in a joint inversion scheme, with the
478 purpose of enhancing AEM resolution where ground-based EM data are available and
479 extend the results to larger areas where only AEM might be available in an upscaling
480 effort: this will be the goal of near to come future studies.

481 Based on our results we conclude that the use of contact-less electro-magnetometer
482 surveys hold the promise of becoming basic tools for peat thickness mapping, a
483 necessary information in order to characterize these valuable natural carbon reservoirs.

484

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487 Technologies for Peatland Detection and Characterization) that has received funding
22

Commented [DSSP6]: Lines 485-486: As "information" is used as a plural noun here, I suggest deleting the indefinite article "a" at the end of line 485.

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494 The authors declare the following competing interests: Andrea Viezzoli is the head of
495 a small company that provides technical support for the analyses of AEM data.

496 FDEM and ERT data used for this paper are freely available through
497 OpenAIRE/Zenodo at <http://...> with DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3786404](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3786404).

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708

709 **Appendix**

710 a

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712 b

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714 c

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716 d

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718

719 Fig. A1 – AEM resistivity model retrieved for the longest (northern) flight line using:
720 a) 40 layers and starting with initial conductivity of $30 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$; b) 40 layers and starting
721 with initial conductivity of $5 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$; c) 5 layers and starting with initial conductivity of
722 $30 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$; d) 5 layers and starting with initial conductivity of $5 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$.